
Isolation and Partial Characterization of a Flavone from Sudanese *Ammi visnaga* (Umbellifereae)

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Abstract *Ammi visnaga* is widely used in Sudanese herbal medicine where it is used against a wide range of diseases including asthma, urinary calculi and mild anginal symptoms. The plant is diuretic and is claimed to relieve menstruation pain. *Ammi visnaga* contains, among others, khellin, khellinol, amiol, khellol and khellinin. It also contains coumarins and a fixed oil.

This study was undertaken to investigate the major flavonoid of *Ammi visnaga*. The flavonoids were extracted with ethanol and the crude extract was purified by thin layer chromatography where a pure flavone was isolated. The structure of the isolated flavone has been partially characterized by some spectral data (UV and ¹HNMR).

Keyword: *Ammi visnaga*, Isolation, Flavonoid, Flavone, Partial Structure

1. Introduction

The genus *Ammi* is a genus in the family Umbellifereae containing some bioactive constituents like flavonoids and coumarins. The medicinally important *Ammi visnaga* has a wide distribution area including Europe, western Asia, Mediterranean region and north Africa [1-3].

Ammi visnaga is traditionally used by many communities against asthma, urinary calculi and mild anginal symptoms [4]. The plant is reported as diuretic and claimed to relieve menstruation pain [4]. *Ammi visnaga* contains, among others, khellin, khellinol, amiol, khellol and khellinin. It also contains coumarins and a fixed oil [5-9].

The antimicrobial activity of *Ammi visnaga* extracts against a panel of human pathogens has been demonstrated [10]. The essential oil from this species is claimed to exhibit antimicrobial activity [11]. *In vivo* studies have revealed that *Ammi visnaga* induced relaxation of smooth muscles including the urethra and coronary arteries [12].

It has also been shown that the plant has a protective effect against kidney stone formation. Two of its constituents – khellin and visnagin- protected against calcium oxalate- induced cell damage in model animals [13].

2. Materials and Methods

Materials

Plant material

The seeds of *Ammi visnaga* were collected from Nyala- west Sudan. The plant was authenticated by the Department of Phytochemistry and Taxonomy, National Research Center, Khartoum.

Instruments

UV spectrum was run on a Shimadzu UV – 2401PC UV- Visible Spectrophotometer. NMR spectrum was measured on a Joel ECA 500 NMR Spectrophotometer.

Methods

Extraction and isolation of flavonoids

Dry powdered plant material (1Kg) was macerated with 95% ethanol (5L) for 72hr at room temperature with occasional shaking and then filtered off. The extraction process was repeated two more times with the same solvent. Combined filtrates were concentrated under reduced pressure at 40° C until all ethanol was removed yielding a crude product. Preparative thin layer chromatography was carried out for the ethanol extract using BAW (butanol: acetic: water 4:1:5 upper layer) as solvent system. The developed chromatograms were dried, observed in UV light (366, 254 nm) and then determined with smooth lines using a pencil and scratched.

The equivalent bands from each plate were then slurred with methanol. After filtration, the solvent was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. In this way a flavonoid- compound I (R_f 0.66) was isolated and recrystallized from absolute ethanol.

3. Results and Discussion

Characterization of compound I

The UV spectrum (Fig.1) of compound I gave λ_{max} 248, 303 nm which is consistent with the absorption of flavones. These compounds consistently show band I in the range: λ_{max} 300-356nm. In contrast, the closely related flavonols absorb in the range: λ_{max} 358-390nm (band I) [14].

Figure 1: UV spectrum of compound I

The hydroxylation pattern of the isolated flavones has been studied via various UV shift reagents (sodium methoxide, sodium acetate, aluminium chloride and boric acid). These reagents produce diagnostic bathochromic shifts [14] in presence of specific hydroxylation pattern. Sodium methoxide can detect 3- and 4'-OH functions, while sodium acetate is diagnostic of a 7-OH group. Aluminium chloride can detect 3-, 5-OH functions as well as catechol systems. Boric acid is helpful in the specific detection of catechol moieties [14,15].

The sodium methoxide spectrum (Fig.2) did not reveal any bathochromic shift indicating absence of both 3- and 4'-hydroxylation.

Figure 2: Sodium methoxide spectrum of compound I

No bathochromic shift was detected in the sodium acetate spectrum (Fig.3) suggesting absence of a 7-OH function.

Figure 3: Sodium acetate spectrum of compound I

The aluminium chloride spectrum (Fig. 4) also failed to show a bathochromic shift indicating absence of 3- and 5-OH functions as well as catechol systems.

Figure 4: Aluminium chloride spectrum of compound I

The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum (Fig. 5) showed: δ 1.22(3H), δ 1.69(6H) assigned for three methyl groups. The resonance at δ 4.17(3H) is due to a methoxyl function. The signals at δ 6.42 and δ 6.45ppm accounts for C-6 and C-8 protons respectively. The C-8 proton usually resonates at lower field relative to C-6 proton due to the deshielding influence [14] of the oxygen atom at position -1. Other aromatic protons appeared at δ 7.17, δ 7.68 and δ 8.12ppm (the resonances at δ 2.50 and δ 3.30 ppm are due to solvent (DMSO) residual protons and residual water respectively).

Figure 5: $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum of compound I

On the basis of the above spectral data the following partial structure was assigned for compound I:

Compound I

A future 2D NMR experiments (^1H COSY NMR, HMBC, HSQC) may fully elucidate the structure of this flavone.

Conclusion

The major flavonoid (a flavones) from *Ammi visnaga* has been isolated via chromatographic techniques and a partial structure has been proposed on the basis of some spectral data.

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